

Forecasting Family Fracture: A Data-Driven Approach to Predicting Divorce in Refugee Camps

Senthil Kumar, A.P.

Jigjiga University

Abstract

Divorce rates within refugee populations have been escalating, particularly in settings marked by displacement, poverty, and uncertainty. This study investigates the factors contributing to divorce among married couples in Sheder refugee camp. Employing an explanatory research design, quantitative data was collected from 97 divorced refugees. Quantitative analysis, specifically multiple regression, identified economic hardship, substance abuse, mental health issues, and cultural and social factors as significant predictors of divorce. The study underscores the urgent need for comprehensive interventions, including culturally sensitive counseling services and community-based support programs, to address these issues and mitigate the negative consequences of divorce on individuals and families in refugee contexts.

Keywords: Divorce, Social Factors, Economical Factors, Psychological Factors and Multiple regression.

I Introduction

A wealth of international research has explored various aspects of divorce across different cultures and customs. [1-6] have examined the causes of divorce. Their findings indicate that key factors include infidelity, behavioral and sexual incompatibility, substance abuse, early marriage, and economic and psychological dependency. Other potential contributors to divorce highlighted in their research include infertility, inadequate conflict resolution skills, poor communication, peer influence, parental involvement in marital issues, experiences of parental divorce, and low educational attainment among partners. Additionally, the studies suggest that religion, cultural and ethnic differences between partners, the contrast between rural and urban living, and the presence of children in the household may also play significant roles in the likelihood of divorce.

According to Ethiopia's Revised Family Code (RFC), specifically Article 96, marriage is defined as a legally recognized union between a man and a woman. It's common for partners in a marriage to face disagreements. When couples cannot resolve their differences through constructive dialogue, they often turn to divorce as a final option. Divorce, the formal end of a marriage, has become a significant social concern, frequently stemming from conflicts between spouses that can range from minor disagreements to serious disputes. In many cases, a couple's inability to address their issues leads them to consider divorce. However,

divorce itself does not offer a permanent solution for the parties involved; it can create additional challenges that contribute to broader societal problems. Today, divorce is recognized as a prevalent issue impacting communities across society [7].

Divorce can have profoundly negative consequences for both individuals and their children, often leading to intricate challenges. Children of divorced parents frequently face a heightened sense of insecurity, as they are directly affected by the turmoil, impacting their academic performance and social interactions. A breakdown of the family unit fails to provide a stable environment for its members, which can unfortunately lead to instances of "child abuse" with lasting effects. Despite efforts from the government and community to support family cohesion, divorce remains an unfortunate reality in many lives [4].

Conversely, research conducted [8] reveals that two-thirds of women who opt for divorce make this choice within the first five years of marriage. Additionally, 45% of first marriages in Ethiopia end in divorce within 30 years. Such a high divorce rate is concerning within Ethiopian culture. This study aims to explore the primary causes and effects of divorce among married couples at the Shedder refugee camp..

Globally, divorce rates have been experiencing periodic increases. Studies by [9] analyzed divorce trends in the USA and Ethiopia, respectively. Their findings indicate that one-third of first marriages end within ten years, and one-fifth conclude within five years. Additionally, marriages involving teenagers tend to dissolve more quickly than those of women who marry at age 20 or older. In Ethiopia, 45% of first marriages result in divorce within 30 years, and two-thirds of women who seek divorce do so within the first five years of marriage. These findings suggest that, despite variations in economic, social, and cultural contexts, divorce rates are on the rise in both regions.

Research conducted [10-13] aimed to identify and mitigate the impacts of divorce. Their findings indicate that divorce is associated with ongoing conflict between former spouses, diminished emotional support, financial challenges, a weakening of family structures, and disruptions in parent-child relationships. Additionally, it often leads to harmful conflict resolution strategies, reduced social skills in children, early loss of virginity, and a compromised sense of gender identity in young adults. Furthermore, divorce can create obstacles in dating, increase cohabitation rates, raise expectations of future divorces, and decrease the desire to have children.

Preliminary data from the Vital Events Registration Office at the Shedder refugee camp indicates that over 320 couples divorced between 2018 and 2022, primarily due to ineffective traditional arbitration in resolving marital issues. This averages out to 64 families dissolving each year, resulting in the separation of 918 children—376 boys and 542 girls—from one or both parents. Despite the efforts of various stakeholders, data from the past five years reveal a significant increase in divorce rates within the study area [14].

Given the international literature already in existence, one could conclude that divorce is a thoroughly studied social issue. However, there aren't many studies on divorce and family arbitration in African nations, including Ethiopia. We can learn about the experiences of South Africa, Nigeria, Malawi, Mozambique, and Ethiopia by looking at the literature that has already been published in African nations. The few published and unpublished studies

on divorce in Ethiopia focus on its causes, effects, and prevalence among native Ethiopians. One significant information gap has been found from the aforementioned studies on the reasons of divorce and its effects, which necessitates a thorough investigation of the causes and effects of divorce among refugees.

This study aimed to address notable gaps in research by examining the main causes and effects of divorce among married couples at Shedder Refugee Camp in the Somali Regional State (SRS).

II.Related Work

Marriage marks the beginning of cohabitation and the potential for starting a family. However, divorce is the legal end of that union [15]. This process can have detrimental effects on both society and families, disrupting relationships, complicating child-rearing, and undermining the social and economic stability of mothers and their children [6].

Various theories provide insights into the reasons for divorce and its impact on children, including conflict theory, exchange theory, institutional theory, specialization theory, attachment theory, and family systems theory.

Conflict theory suggests that class oppression within a capitalist society plays a crucial role in divorce. In a cohabitating relationship, power dynamics can become imbalanced, with one partner exerting more influence. Differences in obligations and responsibilities may lead to the dissolution of the marriage. Moreover, this theory posits that social and economic pressures, rather than the dynamics of the couple's relationship, largely drive issues related to divorce[16].

Exchange theory posits that successful marriages are founded on a balance of give and take, in contrast to conflict theory. Couples who actively engage in this reciprocal process are less likely to face dissolution of their marriage. When both partners contribute and feel fulfilled, they tend to experience greater satisfaction and a lower risk of divorce. This theory also suggests that unmet expectations regarding relationship quality can lead to dissatisfaction and ultimately divorce [17].

Conflict theory, rooted in sociology, addresses the inequalities among social classes and the competition for limited resources, such as wealth, political power, and social status. [18] is often credited as a key figure in the development of conflict theory, influenced by the earlier ideas of German philosopher [19]. Hegel's dialectical method proposed that an accepted idea (the thesis) would inevitably be challenged by an opposing idea (the antithesis), leading to a resolution (the synthesis) that merges aspects of both. This new synthesis would then serve as the basis for a new thesis, perpetuating the cycle [20].

In the realm of marriage and family studies, conflict theory helps explain both stability and instability within relationships. It offers insights into the conditions that foster harmonious interactions and the factors that lead to conflict [21]. Since conflict is a natural part of human interactions, understanding how to manage it can illuminate the dynamics of marital stability and instability. Some conflicts, however, are insurmountable, and unresolved

issues can result in divorce. Researchers have identified various processes related to divorce, including emotional, cultural, and economic aspects, that shape the experience of separation [22].

The data collection methods employed in this study sought to uncover the primary factors contributing to marital conflict through the lens of conflict theory. The researcher also aimed to identify the processes associated with the experience of divorce. Various data-gathering tools were utilized to assess the economic, social, and psychological dimensions faced by divorced individuals.

III. Research Methodology

The research focuses on divorce among married couples in Sheder, a kabele within the Fafan Zone of the Somali Regional State, specifically in the Shedder Refugee Camp, which hosts approximately 14,485 Somali refugees. Located about 20 kilometers from Awbare and 50 kilometers from Jigjiga, Sheder is known for its wheat production and has a humid subtropical highland climate with distinct wet and dry seasons. An explanatory research design was employed, prioritizing quantitative data collection and analysis, with a target population of divorced refugees. A sample of 97 respondents, representing 10% of this population, was selected through systematic random sampling. Data collection involved closed-ended questionnaires, translated into English and Somali, while data analysis utilized descriptive and multivariate statistics via SPSS, along with inferential statistics like regression analysis.

About Dataset

Stepwise Multiple Linear Regression Analysis for Independent Variables and Divorce

S. No.	Stressors	r	R ²	R ² Change	B	t	Sig.
1	Economical	0.270	0.073	-0.073	-1.111	-5.523	P < 0.05
2	Sociological	0.314	0.099	0.026	0.424	2.489	P < 0.05
3	Psychological	0.339	0.115	0.016	0.433	2.316	P < 0.05

The statistical analysis revealed that three sub-dimensional factors significantly contribute to the dependent variable, Divorce. Specifically, the Economical, Sociological, and Psychological stressors accounted for variances of 7.3%, 9.9%, and 11.5%, respectively. The regression equation derived from the analysis is as follows:

$$\text{Divorce} = 28.7 + (-1.111) \times \text{Economical} + (0.424) \times \text{Sociological} + (0.433) \times \text{Psychological}$$

The regression model demonstrated strong validity, with significant F-ratios ($F = 23.971, 16.692, \text{ and } 13.124$, all $P < 0.000$). Notably, Psychological stressors had the most substantial influence on divorce, explaining 11.5% of the variance. It is important to mention that other independent variables, including Gender, Age, and Education, were not found to significantly impact divorce, leading to their exclusion from the regression analysis.

IV Conclusion

This research aims to explore the reasons behind divorce among married couples in the Shedder refugee camp in the Somali Regional State. Notably, the rate of divorce in this camp has been steadily rising. Document analysis from 2018 to 2022 indicates an upward trend in divorce rates. The findings suggest that the primary causes of divorce can be categorized into psychological, social, and economic factors. Using regression analysis on the collected data, the study identified these influences more precisely. The results highlight that a significant factor contributing to divorce is the lack of understanding between spouses. Additionally, economic challenges such as unemployment and social influences, including family interference, peer pressure, and habits like smoking and chewing khat, also play crucial roles in marital breakdowns. This study identifies three key factors predicting divorce among refugees: 1. Psychological factors, 2. Sociological factors, and 3. Economic factors. In conclusion, the study warns that without intervention, the rising divorce rate will likely lead to ongoing psychosocial and economic crises in the region.

REFEREFNCES

- [1] Amato, P. R. and D. Previti. (2009). *People's Reasons for Divorcing: The Pennsylvania State University*. Journal of Family Issues, Vol. 24. 602-626.
- [2] Furtado, D., Miriam M. & A. Sevilla-Sanz. (2011). *Does Culture Affect Divorce Decisions? Evidence from European Immigrants in the USA*. London: University of Oxford.
- [3] Adegoke, T. G. (2017). *Socio-cultural Factors as Determinants of Divorce Rates among Women of Reproductive Age in Ibadan Metropolis*. Nigeria. Ibadan: University of Ibadan
- [4] Serkalem Bekele. (2013). *Divorce: Its Cause and Impact on the Lives of Divorced Women and Their Children*. Unpublished Master's thesis, Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia. Retrieved from <http://www.aau.edu.et:8080>
- [5] Becker, G. S. (2009). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago press.
- [6] Askalemariam Adamu and Minwagaw Temesgen. (2016). *Divorce in east Gojjam zone: rates, causes and consequences*. Debre Markos University, Ethiopia.
- [7] Kulik, L. and Kasa, Y. A. (2014). *Adjustment to Divorce: A Comparison of Ethiopian*

- Immigrant and Israeli-Born Men. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 191–208
- [8] Dana Tilson and Ulla Larsen. (2010). *Divorce in Ethiopia: The Impact of Early Marriage And Childlessness*. *Journal of Biosocial Science*, 32 pp 355-372.
- [9] Bramlett, M.D. and Mosher, W.D. (2009). First Marriage Dissolution, Divorce, and Remarriage: United States. *Advance Data*, Number 323, May 31, Department of Health and Human Services, Washington DC.
- [10] Amato, P.R. (2006). *Father-child relations; Mother-child relations; and offspring psychological well-being in early adulthood*. *Journal of Marriage and Family issues*:1031-1042.
- [11] Palosaari U.K. and Aro H.M. (2007). *Parental divorce, self-esteem and depression: an intimate relationship as a protective factor in young adulthood*. Finland: University of Tampere
- [12] Landucci, N. (2008). *The Impact of Divorce on Children: What School Counselors Need to Know*. Madison: University of Wisconsin-Stout
- [13] Hewitt, B., Skrbis, Z., and Mark, W. (2009). *The Association Between Parental Divorce and Adolescents' Expectations of Divorce*. Australia: University of Queensland.
- [14] Refugee and Returnee Service. (2023). *Five years report. Jigjiga Branch Office*. Jigjiga, Ethiopia.
- [15] Seid, J. (2014). *Psychosocial and Economical Consequences of Divorce in Muslim Community in Gondar City Administration*. Gondar Faculty of Social Sciences and the Humanities School of Sociology and Social Work: Master thesis Vol 2, Issue 4, 2014.
- [16] Geoffrey, M. (2016). *Conflict theory and divorce*. London: Sage publication.
- [17] Donovan, R. L., & Jackson, B. L. (2015). *Deciding to divorce: A process guided by social exchange*. *social exchange*.
- [18] Marx, K., & Engels, F. (1848). *The Communist Manifesto*. London: Penguin Classics. (Original work published 1848)
- [19] Hegel, G. W. F. (1807). *Phenomenology of Spirit* (A. V. Miller, Trans.). Oxford University Press. (Original work published 1807)
- [20] Russell, B. (2007). *A history of Western philosophy*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
- [21] Sprey, J. (2009). *The family as a system in conflict*. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 699-706.
- [22] Shehan, C. L., and K. C. W. Kammeyer. (2010). *Marriages and families: Reflections of a gendered society*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.